

SUPERIORITY POTENCY OF CHRIST'S ἑΦΑΠΑΞ SACRIFICE IN HEBREWS 9-10 TO IMBORIVUNGU CULT

¹Abel Aor Inyaregh and ²Matthew Vanen Chiangi

Article Info

Keywords: Once and for all, sacrifice, Christ, imborivungu, Hebrews

DOI

10.5281/zenodo.19552856

Abstract

The superiority of the ἑφάπαξ sacrifice of Christ in Hebrews 9-10 abhors the continuity of human bloodshed and annuls any foreseeable sacrifices. Christ's sacrifice is a single event that can be regarded as the prohibition of any other analogous happening; once and for all, and never again. The practice of the imborivungu cult, which accompanies human bloodshed, is an abomination associated with the dark side of Tiv culture. This is capable of leading people to apostasy, which the author of the Hebrews warns against. The unsettling aspect of human sacrifice is not just a ritual act intended to pacify the gods, revitalize destiny, and promote fertility, or bring luck and prosperity to those offering the sacrifice. All human sacrifice formulas are stimulated by egocentricities at the cost of ill-treating others and are therefore repugnant to Jesus's selfless human sacrifice. This study reveals the final human sacrifice in Christ's death.

Introduction

The letter to the Hebrews is unique among its New Testament equivalents in that it is the only canonical writing to offer an exhaustive justification of the high priestly ministry of Christ within a comprehensive dialogue of Israel's cultic theology. It is argued that similar to the ministry of the high priest on Yom Kippur, Christ's priestly offering is made upon his entrance into the heavenly sanctuary instead of at the moment of his crucifixion. The author presents Jesus Christ as the best in all things of salvation by contrasting Him to various aspects of the Jewish system and other entities that would have been of repute to the Jewish person. The scholarly argument is upheld from biblical study that the overarching concern of the author of the epistle is Christ's superiority. In this study, the emphasis is shifted to Christ's sacrifice as a "once-for-all" sacrifice that does not give space for another. Coming to terms with Imborivungu in Tiv culture is a blood-sucking deity that requires frequent human sacrifices to guarantee prosperity, affluence, fertility, and good luck. The reconstruction of the notion of God debunked this act. However, the concept of Jesus as the sacrifice is theologically creative and innovative. This paper explores

¹Department of Religion Studies National Open University of Nigeria, University Village, Plot 91, Cadastral Zone, Nnamdi Azikiwe Expressway, Airport Road, Jabi, FCT, Abuja, Nigeria

²Department of Religion and Philosophy, University of Mkar.

these dynamic developments and discusses how they could ultimately lead the Tiv people to abandon the imborvungu cult. Hitherto, it had been largely obvious in the Tiv religion that prosperity was sought through offering human sacrifices. Perhaps more than any other book of the New Testament, Hebrews emphasizes the superiority of Christ's sacrifice to demystify the absolute supremacy and sufficiency of Christ as God's full and final revelation to His people. In so doing, the OT sacrifices cease to operate, thereby imborvungu's sacrifice on human blood has to be discontinued since there is no more shedding of blood for any reason. The study adopts the rhetorical method, which examines the author's ways of expressing his message to unravel the theological significance in Hebrews that will erode the menace of imborvungu in Tiv land. The Superiority of the ἐφάπαξ Sacrifice of Christ demonstrated an end to the OT sacrifices and any other anticipatable sacrifices.

Superiority of Christ as the Only High Priest after the Order of Melchizedek

The author of the Hebrews presents Jesus as the Priest according to Melchizedek's order, as prophesied in Ps 110:4². In Hebrews 7–9, the exalted Christ is labeled as exercising a liturgical ministry in the heavenly sanctuary, on which the first and second temples were patterned (Exod 25:40). Having offered a once-for-all sacrifice of himself (Heb 9:26; 10:12), he has entered the holy place, taking with him his own blood (Heb 9:12, 24) to perform a priestly act of intercession for his people (Heb 7:25; 8:1–3). Schrenk argues that Christ's priesthood differs from the Old Testament priesthood in many respects³. To support this claim, he asserts that Christ's priesthood is in the order of Melchizedek (Heb. 7:1-19), not Aaron or Levites⁴. Christ's priesthood supersedes the OT temporal system of priesthood, which has no guarantee of washing away sins⁵. On the same page, Lindars describes Jesus's eternal priesthood in the essence and likeness of Melchizedek, the High Priest of the Most High God and King of Salem (Heb 7:11-28)⁶. According to Ladd, Jesus is a High Priest forever⁷. Gossai agrees with Lindars, as he portrays Christ as the Davidic King-Priest⁸ and as the Son of God (Heb 1:2, 5; 4:14; 5:5; 6:6; 7:3). The Hebrew attest that Jesus the High Priest came to earth once through the incarnation⁹.

Many scholars key into the notion expressing Christ who committed Himself to submitting his body to accomplishing what all burnt and sinful offerings were not capable of accomplishing¹⁰. Chester presents Jesus as the unique High Priest who offered Himself once and for all in an atoning sacrifice, accordingly declaring the ceaseless, fruitless sacrifices of the Jewish rites as archaic.¹¹ According to Morris, Christ appeared in the presence of God as both the High Priest and the casualty¹². This entrance as the one who sacrifices himself was made once for all time (Heb. 9:25, 26c, 28a). Hawthorne elaborates that Christ will never be sacrificed again and that His sacrifice is complete, perfect, and final¹³.

Chapter 9 is part of this central Christological description of the Hebrews. It addressed Christians of a Hellenistic and Jewish background who, from the authorial perspective, were in danger of backsliding from faith in Christ

²For example, connecting God's declaration (ὁμῶς) of an eternal priest (Σὺ ἱερεὺς εἰς τὸν αἰῶνα) with that of Jesus's eternal Sonship, it can be deduced that Christ was both a Son and a Priest from all eternity. The author asserts that Melchizedek has 'neither beginning of days nor end of life' (μῆτε ἀρχὴν ἡμερῶν μῆτε ζῶης τέλος ἔχων).

³K. G. Schrenk, Role of the priests. In: G. Kittel and Friedrich, G. (eds). Theological Dictionary of the NT Grand Rapids (Michigan: W.B. Eerdmans, 1988), 358.

⁴Shiffman, L. H. Temple, sacrifice, and priesthood in the Epistle to the Hebrews and the Dead Sea Scrolls. In: F.G. Martinez, Echoes from the Caves: Qumran and the NT (Leiden: Brill series 2009), 172.

⁵The Melchizedek order underlines the superiority of Christ's priesthood over that of the Levites (Heb. 7:15-22). Christ's priesthood is an authoritative ensuing a vow made by God (Heb. 7:21). Christ's priesthood is eternal and eschatological (Heb. 3:1-7:28), equated to the time-based character of the Old Testament priesthood (Shiffman Temple, sacrifice, 172). The eternity of the Christ priesthood is ascribed to the Sonship of Christ (Heb. 4:14, 7:28). Christ is sinless (Heb. 7:25-28) and did not have to sacrifice for His own sins, thus making Him a perfect obligatory for high priesthood. Christ was hired to high priesthood by God (Heb. 5:5-10, 7:17, 21).

⁶Barnabas Lindars, SSF the Theology of the Letter to the Hebrews (New York: Cambridge University Press, 1991), 77-79.

⁷Hebrews 5:5-6, 9-10.

⁸Hemchand Gossai, Studies in Biblical Literature: The King-Priest of Psalm 110 in Hebrews (New York: Peterlang, 2001), 230-231.

⁹Hebrews 5:5-6, 9-10; He died once upon the cross, was buried, and was raised from the dead on the third day. Jesus ascended to heaven where He entered once into the holy of holies to offer His own blood so that sinners can be saved. Jesus is now seated at the right hand of His Heavenly Father. Moreover, James Walter Thompson asserts that Jesus is once for all the realistic High Priest. (Hebrews 9 and Hellenistic concept of sacrifice. JBL vol.98, 4 (1979): 567-578).

¹⁰Richard C. H. Lenski, The interpretation of the Epistle to the Hebrews and the The Epistle to James Minneapolis: Ausburg Publishing House, 1966; Franz Delitzsch, Commentary on the Epistle to the Hebrews vol.2. (Minneapolis: Klock & clock Christian Publishers, 1978); Robert H. Smith, Ausburg Commentary of the New Testament: Hebrews (Minneapolis: Ausburg Publishing House, 1984), 122-23.

¹¹Arthur N. Chester, Hebrews: The Final Sacrifice." In Sacrifice and Redemption, ed. Sykes, S. W. (New York: Cambridge University Press, 1991), 57.

¹²Leon Morris, Hebrews, Bible Study Commentary. (Grand Rapids, MI: Zondervan House Publisher, 1988), 290.

¹³Gerald Hawthorne, Hebrews. In: F.F. Bruce (ed.), Zondervan Bible commentary (Grand Rapids, MI: Zondervan, 2008), 1537.

and deteriorating to their fetish earlier religious practices. In relation to this context, Hebrews 9 interprets Jesus as Christ to prevent this backslide. Hebrews 9 interprets Jesus as Christ by presenting him as “a high priest of the upcoming good things” (ἀρχιερεὺς τῶν γενομένων ἀγαθῶν, Heb 9:11). Nevertheless, this motif infiltrates several chapters of Hebrews; the high priestly role of Jesus is overtly declared.

In Hebrews, Martin Luther expounds on the priesthood of Christ, which is treated as a twofold priesthood. The former priesthood was a material one, with material adornment, tabernacle, sacrifices, and pardons embedded in ritual. The new order is a spiritual priesthood, with spiritual adornments, spiritual tabernacles, and sacrifices in all that pertains to it¹⁴. As stated by Leviticus 16, the high priest must enter the holy place once a year with the blood of rams and other offerings, and with these, make formal reconciliation for the people. This ceremony typified that Christ, the true Priest, should once die for us to achieve the true atonement for us. However, the former sacrifice, which had to be repeated every year, was only a temporary and imperfect atonement; it was not eternally sufficient, as is the atonement of Christ. Although we fall and sin repeatedly, we have confidence that the blood of Christ does not fall or sin; it remains resolute before God, and the expiation is everlasting and eternal. Grace is everlastingly transformed under its supremacy, without work or merit on our part, as long as we do not stand distant in unbelief¹⁵. Moreover, Luther further clarified that those who might benefit from Christ’s priesthood do not all, nevertheless, do not receive him. Only those called to be heirs eternal, the elect, receive the Spirit¹⁶. Following the path of Luther on the elect who will benefit from Christ’s sacrifice, Calvin, Brown, and Owen aver that Christ’s death is connected with numerous sons (Heb 2:10), that is, those who are purified (Heb 2:11) and the lineage of Abraham (Heb 2:16), and established that Christ died for all of the saved, that is, the elect¹⁷.

The author of Hebrews stresses that Jesus Christ made the all-sufficient atonement through his obedient sacrifice, through which the believer’s conscience could be fully cleansed. To have a cleansed conscience preordained as being unfettered from the agony of guilt. This entails the sanctification of the soul. Thus, the cleansing of the conscience opened the door for the believer to have the privilege of grace’s transforming power. By implication, the believer was equipped to enter into God’s glory. Christ’s compliance enables the righteous to live in compliance and fellowship with God (Heb. 10:5–10). Individually, a believer comes to God’s ‘throne’ to find grace for living this life of faithfulness (4:14–16; 10:19–25)¹⁸. Articulating on 1 Pet 2:24–25, John Calvin once again makes it obvious that by Christ’s death, He has saved and restored us to life, from which it follows that we are so bound to Him that we ought joyfully look at him as a model¹⁹.

Old Testament high priests were honest and devoted representatives. Nevertheless, they were similarly sinful human beings like those they were representing; hence, they offered sacrifices for their own sins, as specified in Hebrews 5:3²⁰. The author of Hebrews considers Jesus the representative or mediator of men before God. He was labeled as a High Priest (Heb 5:5), and every high priest is assigned responsibilities on behalf of the people, specifically, to offer sacrifices to God, as Hebrews 5:1 illustrates.²¹

The perception that Jesus is the “better,” or superior whether as the Son of God superior to angels (2:9), the Priest-King whose priestly order is superior to that Levitical priesthood (4:14–5:11; 7:18:6), the Mediator whose new covenant is superior to the old covenant (8:7–13), the Priest whose heavenly Sanctuary is superior to the

¹⁴Martin Luther (1483–1546) “Christ Our Great High Priest.” *The Sermons of Martin Luther VII*. (Minneapolis, MN: The Luther Press, 1909), 163–167.

¹⁵Luther (1483–1546) “Christ Our Great High Priest”

¹⁶Luther (1483–1546) “Christ Our Great High Priest”

¹⁷John Calvin, *The Epistle of Paul the Apostle to the Hebrews and the First and Second Epistles of St. Peter* (Grand Rapids, MI: University of Michigan Press, 1963), 24; John Owen D. D., *Hebrews: The Epistle of Warning* (Michigan: Kregel Publications, 1968), 361.

¹⁸Gareth Lee Cockerill, *The Epistle to the Hebrews, the New International Commentary on the New Testament* (Grand Rapids, MI: Eerdmans, 2012), 386.

¹⁹For example, Calvin, *Epistle of Paul the Apostle to the Hebrews*, 278.

²⁰I. Howard Marshall, *New Testament Theology: Many Witnesses One Gospel* (Downers Grove, Illinois: Intervarsity Press, 2004), 608.

²¹Leon Morris, *New Testament Theology* (Michigan: Academie Books, Grand Rapids, Zondervan Publishing House, 1986), 305.

earthly sanctuary (9:1-22), or the Sacrifice whose substitution is superior to that of the earthly sanctuary's sacrifices (9:23-10:25) is the all-embracing subject of the epistle, and its thrust on Christ sacrifice.²²

Scholer emphatically attests that Christ was given heavenly high priesthood on entering heaven after he offered himself once and for all as an offering and a sacrifice on the cross to elucidate on Jesus' priesthood.²³ Likewise, the designation of heavenly high priesthood is not from eternity but attained instantly when he converted to obedient sacrifice and mediator between God and his people. As an earthly High Priest, Christ commiserated with the people (Heb. 4:15, 5:2) and offered a worthwhile sacrifice once and for all. As a signal for the finished work he has done, he is seated at the right hand of God (Heb. 10:12). Following the same line of thought with additional assertion, Hagner upholds that Christ is the mediator of a superior covenant, who, through his blood, installed a New Covenant (Heb. 9:15a) of which He was a mediator²⁴.

Hagner acknowledges Jesus as the high priest as a mediator who occupies two offices: that of a prophet and that of a priest. As a prophet, he represents God to humankind, and as a priest, he represents humankind to God²⁵. These roles are interwoven and cannot be unglued. As a full deity and human being, Christ empowers Himself to be the all-sufficient sacrifice that establishes the New Covenant. Attridge agrees with Hagner on this point of view and adds that Christ's role as a mediator is to intercede for humanity and present their petitions to God.²⁶ Again, Attridge sheds more light on Christ's mediatory role as being capable of mediating for our past, present, and future actions²⁷. Hawthorne, expounding on the mediatory role of Christ, underlines that a will was authorized for believers to get their inheritance when Christ died.²⁸

The predominant message of the Hebrews is that Jesus Christ is better, greater, superior, and more operational than any character, incident, or organization in the Old Testament.²⁹ The author of Hebrews has contended the superiority and supremacy of Jesus Christ and His revelation by the God of the Hebrews. He is superior because of who he is and what he did. Jesus is God and a substitute for sin. Jesus made the full and final sacrifice for the purging of sins. The Old Covenant was a ritual and coercion; its protocols were intended to point to God's holiness. Nevertheless, it had one major error: it did not call to the humankind's heart. Hearts could not be transformed; there was only obligation and responsibility. The priests and the system only romanced with the external surface that continually required purification, coming from reluctant people bringing their reluctant animals. Jesus, the disposed sacrifice, became our salvation. He laid down his own life for his own. The Prodigious Cleanser addressed our inward consciences, minds, and hearts. Christ obliges us to be appreciative and astounding by His Person and work, so we will have love and an unaffected reaction of the heart that constructs. His own are drawn to Him in their hearts because He is the Better Sacrifice (John 10:14-18; Gal. 5).

In the first room, the Levite priests performed their duties of ministering before the Lord and offering sacrifices for the people. This room was called the holy place. The High Priest would enter the second room once a year. This room was called the "Holy of Holies" or the "Most Holy Place." A heavy veil or curtain unglued the two rooms. The High Priest would have to prepare himself before entering the Holy of Holies. The purpose of the entrance of the High Priest into the Most Holy Place is given in Hebrews 9:7³⁰. On the Day of Atonement, the High Priest enters the Holy of Holies. He would sprinkle blood from a bull on the mercy seat for his sins, and

²²When Christ offered Himself on the cross, it was a once-and-for-all substitutionary sacrifice to God on behalf of the sins of the past, present, and future. There is no further payment needed, as Jesus uttered, "tetelestai" He affirmed forever, it is finished. Chapter 9 of Hebrews features a new treatise about sacrifice, arguing that the unique sacrifice of Jesus makes all others redundant.

²³Scholer, J. M. *Proleptic Priests: Priesthood in the Epistle of Hebrews*. JSNT, Supplement Series 49 (Sheffield: JSOT. 1991): 83, 85.

²⁴Hagner, D. A. *Encountering Hebrews: An Exposition* (Grand Rapids, Michigan: Baker Academic, 2002), 122.

²⁵Hagner, *Encountering Hebrews*, 122.

²⁶See Harold W. Attridge, *Epistle to the Hebrews*, pp. 57–76. In: D.N. Freedman, *the Anchor Bible Dictionary*, 3 (New York: Doubleday, 1992), 102.

²⁷Attridge, *Epistle*, 254.

²⁸Hawthorne, *Hebrews*, 1557.

²⁹See Cockerill, *the Epistle to the Hebrews*, 22; Raymond Brown, "Pilgrimage in Faith: The Christian Life in Hebrews," *Southwestern Journal of Theology* 28 no. 1 (1985): 28–35.

³⁰But only the high priest went into the inner room, and then only once a year, all alone, and always with blood that he sprinkled on the mercy seat as an offering to God to cover his own mistakes and sins and the mistakes and sins of all the people.

then he would sprinkle blood from a goat on the mercy seat for all the sins of Israel. The blood of the goat covered Israel's sins. The word "atone" means to "cover over." God's law demanded death as the punishment for sin. When God saw the death of the blameless sacrifice for Israel's sin, He was pleased that the demands of His law had been met. Sacrificing an animal on an altar did not wash away sin. Blood conciliated the wrath of a Holy God against sin. This was a momentary cover for Israel's sins. Jesus would offer a better sacrifice and an everlasting atonement for our sins³¹.

(v. 15) 'by the means of death,' Jesus is our High Priest who paid a high price for our redemption³². The salvation of sinners necessitated the shedding of the precious blood of Jesus (1 Peter 1:18-19). Jesus was slaughtered as a lamb. Battered and injured for our sins, Jesus hung on the cross. (Isa. 53:3-7) The Father would have perceived the pain as Jesus cried out, 'My God, my God, why hast thou forsaken me?' However, the Father recognized the priceless blood Jesus was shedding for sinners.

The Superiority of Christ's Unique Blood Sacrifice as ἐφάπαξ "Once and for All"

The Author of Hebrews articulates that when Christ came as a high priest of the upcoming good things, then through the greater and perfect tent (not made with hands, that is, not of this creation), he entered once for all into the sanctuary, not with the blood of goats and calves (οὐδὲ δι' αἵματος τράγων καὶ μόσχων), but with his own blood, thus procuring eternal redemption (διὰ δὲ τοῦ ἰδίου αἵματος εἰσηλθεν ἐφάπαξ εἰς τὰ ἅγια αἰώνιαν λύτρωσιν εὐράμενος) (9:11-12).

Christ entered the heavenly holy of holies once and for all (ἐφάπαξ)³³. Christ's blood cleanses the conscience, removes sin and guilt from sinners' conscience, and sanctifies sinners.³⁴ In the Old Testament, sacrifice finally characterized the final perfect sacrifice of Jesus, the final substitute³⁵. The drive of Jesus' sacrifice is to eliminate sin. Here, the phrase "once for all" is important. It is derived from the Greek word "hapax" (ἅπαξ) or "ephapax" (ἐφάπαξ). This implies "a single occurrence to the elimination of any other parallel happening; once and for all, once and never again." Jesus' coming and death on the cross materialized once in history and will never occur again. Yet it impacts the past, present and future eternally." Christ's coming and death on the cross are not simply. The Eternal God acted in history and impacted all eternity³⁶. Hawthorne upholds the eschatological significance of a perfect sacrifice of Christ, and nothing stands between it and the second coming of Christ³⁷.

The aforementioned portrays a large gap in the use of this participle in Hebrews 10:11 for the Old Testament priests. This scrupulous use of tenses transpires throughout the Hebrews. As the author of Hebrews communicates about the Aaronic high priest, he consistently uses the present tense to underscore the incessant nature of their sacrifices (Heb 5:1, 3; 8:3a, 4; 9:7; 10:1, 2, 8). In contrast, when he communicates Christ's offering, he uses the

³¹For example, Morris said that the practical fact about Leviticus high priests can also be applied to Jesus. His being really human, which is very substantial, as the author of Hebrews stresses, makes him eligible to be a High Priest. He is certainly proficient of commiserating with the feebleness of human beings because he is part of the human lineage (New Testament, 305-306).

³²The blood of goats and calves could not atone for our sins. Jesus entered the holy place only once to obtain eternal salvation for us. The sinless, perfect Son of God bore our sins in His own body on the tree (1 Peter 2:24). We have been saved by the blood of the Lamb. (Mark 10:45; 1 Tim 4:15. 2:6) The worth of Christ's sacrifice of Himself cannot be calculated or measured. The kingly Son of God dying for sinful people is beyond our knowledge. The animals that were sacrificed on the altar were not willing to die, but Jesus enthusiastically died for us. He gave himself for us, that he might save us from all sin, and purify a peculiar people, enthusiastic of good works (Titus 2:14 KJV).

³³Homer Austin Kent, Jr., stated that Jesus' sacrifice and bloodshed stemmed eternal salvation for its assurances, contrasting the annual, reiterative, and fleeting atonement that was obligatory in the old covenantal structure (The Epistle to the Hebrews: A Commentary [Grand Rapids: Baker Book House, 1974], 171).

³⁴Donald Guthrie, the Letter to the Hebrews: An Introduction and Commentary (Leicester: Inter-varsity Press, 1983) 189.

³⁵Youngblood, Ronald. F. Nelson's Bible Dictionary: An Authoritative one volume Reference Work on the Bible with full color illustrations (Nashville: Thomas, 1997). Jesus came to earth once by the means of virgin birth. He died once upon the cross, was buried, and was raised from the dead on the third day. Jesus ascended to heaven where He entered once into the holy place to offer His own blood so that sinners could be saved. Jesus is now seated at His Heavenly Father's right hand. Jesus is once for all our faithful High Priest.

³⁶Christ's sacrifice has an eternal effect on the past, present, and future. Christ died once for all and completely and eternally solved the problem of sin. Christ defeated the power of death through his resurrection and lives forever. The letter to the Hebrews develops an inimitable Christological and soteriological concept of Jesus as both a high priest and unique sacrifice. In doing so, the Hebrews remain largely faithful to the cult traditions of Second Temple Judaism. Though the effects of the sacrifice of Jesus Christ are eternal, His sacrifice was a "once-for-all" sacrifice (7:27; 9:12; 10:20).as our high priest. This is why Christ's sacrifice transcends time.

³⁷Hawthorne, Hebrews (1538).

aurist participle to underline its exceptional output and non-repetitive nature, never to be repeated, as depicted in Hebrews 8:3b; 9:14, 28; 10:12.

Dunnill states that the aim of Christ's sacrifice is the forgiveness of all human purposeful and involuntary sins contaminated within the Old Covenant and in the future. Christ's sacrifice canceled and detached our sin, punishment, and curse, like the scapegoat dispatched by the priest to the desert³⁸. The Hebrews affirms that Christ entered heaven and, through his own sacrifice that happened only once, efficiently eradicated sin for all time (9:23–28)³⁹. On the “once-for-all sacrifice of Christ”, Martin Luther accuses Rome of forsaking the once-for-all sacrifice of Calvary in favor of the multitude of sacrifices offered at consecutive Masses. He emphasizes the role of the Mass as a money-making scheme that enables the clergy to swindle the laity to keep the body and soul together in the most contented manner possible: a holy rite that has been shamefully commercialized⁴⁰.

The author of Hebrews tries to emphasize that animal sacrifices were not the sacrifices that God desired⁴¹. Jesus Christ is the only priest who can sufficiently meet the requirements of His people because He is holy, spotless, pure, and exalted above the heavens (Heb 7:22-26). In 9:12–14, the author offers his most systematic examination of the typological sacrificial rites established by the Mosaic covenant. The author accentuates blood, self-sacrifice, and cleansing throughout the verses. He stated that the goal of Jesus was to enter the heavenly realm and make way for others, and he did what the old covenant failed to do: he expunged sins and bathed the worshiper's conscience. The authorial emphasis in Hebrews 9:12 that Jesus entered heaven “once for all” (ephapax) demonstrates the completely sufficient work of Christ, a term that eliminates both the inevitability and the leeway of recurrence⁴².

In addition, there is a gap in Hebrews concerning the principal mechanisms of the Day of Atonement ceremony, for example, the Azazel or Scapegoat ritual or the seven sacrificial blood sprinklings. Regardless of arousing the image of the Tabernacle sanctuary in Heb 9:1-5, the sacrifice of Christ is somewhat designated in connection with the Mosaic covenant ritual in Exodus 24:8 that occurred before the construction of the Tabernacle (Heb 9:18-22). Lastly, David Moffitt contends that the staging of the blood of the sacrificial animals acknowledged here as their life in the Holy of Holies is efficiently linked with the atonement achieved on Yom Kippur, just as the self-presentation of the resurrected Jesus before God in the heavenly sanctuary is related to the unique type of expiation⁴³.

The outcome of Jesus's self-sacrifice was not fixed at an outward cleansing as was the old covenant⁴⁴. As a substitute, it concentrates on the inward cleansing of the conscience. Moreover, the atonement had the unfathomable impact of purifying it. Both cleansing and refining refer to the same authenticity. Cleansing is the removal of sinful contaminations, while refining connotes “the willingness of the purified heart to draw nearer to God⁴⁵. Cleansing and refining of sin signify the conversion's moral renovation.⁴⁶

The author determines the superiority of Jesus' sacrifice by examining the rate of recurrence with which the earthly high priest had to enter the most holy place for atonement. However, the high priest, in the most earnest,

³⁸John Dunnill, *Covenant and Sacrifice in the Letter to the Hebrews* (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 1992), 172.

³⁹Daniel C. Ullucci, *The Christian Rejection of Animal Sacrifice* (Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2012), 92-95. To buttress this point, contrary to the ritual works of the old covenant, it attests about the superior work of Christ: But when Christ came as high priest of the good things that are now already here, he went through the greater and more perfect tabernacle that is not made with human hands, which implies, it is not a part of this creation. The better blessings have already begun; the author prompts us. We by now have forgiveness and direct entrance to God, since Christ went through the heavenly holy place.

⁴⁰Tappert, Theodore G. (ed.). *Luther's Works* (Philadelphia: Fortress Press, 1955), 293.

⁴¹According to Homer Austin Kent, the Old Testament priests stood daily in the tabernacle, offering the same sacrifices as those offered by the other priests. In addition to the repetitive nature of their sacrifices, the very position of the priest, that is, standing (The Epistle to the Hebrews: A Commentary [Michigan: Baker Book House: 1972], 192), designates their inaptness and ineffectiveness, because they cannot once take away sin (Heb 10:11). John Calvin also anchored this notion of the inadequacy of animal sacrifice (The Epistle of Paul the Apostle to the Hebrews and the first and second Epistles of St. Peter [Grand Rapids, 1963], 134-135).

⁴²William L. Lane, *Hebrews 9–13*, *Word Biblical Commentary 47B* (Dallas: Word Books, 1991), 239.

⁴³For example, see David M. Moffitt, *Atonement and the Logic of Resurrection in the Epistle to the Hebrews*. *NovTSup 141* (Boston: Brill, 2011).

⁴⁴Bruce, F. F. *The Epistle to the Hebrews*, *The New International Commentary on the New Testament*, rev. ed. (Grand Rapids, MI: William B. Eerdmans, 1990), 232.

⁴⁵Garth Lee Cockerill, *The Epistle to the Hebrews*, *The New International Commentary on the New Testament* (Grand Rapids, MI: William B. Eerdmans, 2012), 401.

⁴⁶Luke Timothy Johnson, *Hebrews: A Commentary* (Louisville, KY: Westminster John Knox, 2006), 238.

the paramount of all the rituals of the Jewish cultic structure, had to still do this rite annually; Jesus' work in the sanctuary had to be done only once. The once-and-for-all nature of sacrifice portrays supremacy over the sacrifices of the Jewish people. The author is on the lookout to discuss the superiority of Christ's sacrifice from the recurring sacrifice and application perspective. This gives the evidential impression of how many periods the author references the rate of recurrence, with even the Day of Atonement⁴⁷ ritual, the most sacrosanct of all feast day rituals, had to be reiterated (9:26-28; 10:1-4, 11-14). The reason for this rate of recurrence is that no animal can remove sin and make a person impeccable (10:1-4). The system's weakness aroused God, who offered Christ a body, to be the decisive sacrifice for sin, which would only necessitate happening once (vs. 5). By "one offering," Jesus inviolably reinforces who is being consecrated. Furthermore, the author maintains Jesus' superiority to animals by exhibiting that mortal sacrifices were repetitive and animal sacrifices could not free the conscience of guilt as they were only shades (vs. 1).

In Hebrews 9:26-28, the author tries to demonstrate that Christ's sacrifice cannot be repetitive, disagreeing with this based on Jesus' humanity. Humans have one life to live, and then they die, at which time judgment will come into the world.⁴⁸ Expanding on this view, Westcott asserts that although men die once and come into judgment, Christ died once and will emerge as a judge⁴⁹. The obedient sacrifice of Christ makes the Mosaic covenant archaic with its sacrificial system and propagates a new covenant with the autonomous self-sacrifice of a rational being, Christ Himself (Heb. 10:9). The sanctification that occurs through Christ's sacrifice will not only become a regular way of unfolding the fallouts of His act⁵⁰. This subject is another way of denoting the perfection and cleansing of conscience accomplished through sacrifice. The author of Hebrews ascertains that under the law, almost everything is purified with the blood, and without the shedding of the blood, sin is not forgiven (Heb 9:22).

Hebrews 9:12 reveals that Christ entered once into the Holy Place, that is, Heaven itself, as the author portrays in Hebrews 9:24. Christ entered the glorious place, the residence of God's presence or majesty. At His ascension, He entered into heaven in reverential glory and conquest after defeating Satan, the world, death, Hell, and all the powers assigned to Him. He entered heaven triumphantly and hieratically after making peace and reconciliation through His blood on the cross, sanctioning the covenant and propagating eternal salvation.⁵¹

Christ's seated position indicates that his sacrificial work has been achieved once and forever. The author's additional squabble in establishing the superiority of Christ's sacrifice is that after He had offered Himself, He sat down at the right hand of God (Heb 10:11-14). The author repeats the facts identified in Hebrews 10:1-4, that is, the Old Testament sacrifices were repeatedly reiterated and ineffective⁵². However, in Hebrews 10:12, Jesus sacrificed himself and then sat down. The writer's argument is clear: Christ's sacrifice is instrumental and ultimate; it has fulfilled its purpose of taking away sin and drawing men to God.

Neither by the blood of goats and calves, but by his own blood, he entered once into the holy place, having obtained eternal redemption for us. KJV, 1769; IB' οὐδὲ δι' αἵματος τράγων καὶ μόσχων διὰ δὲ τοῦ ἰδίου αἵματος εἰσῆλθεν ἐράπαξ εἰς τὰ ἅγια αἰωνίαν λύτρωσιν εὐράμενος TR, 1550

Jesus' Once and for All Perfect Sacrifice is Superior to the OT Sacrifices

There is only one wholly all-sufficient sacrifice for sin. It is the death of Christ for sinners. Animal sacrifices could not achieve this. Christ's blood is the only source for God's people to enter into heaven. Without the

⁴⁷Gordon avers that the author of the Epistle has the Day of Atonement in his thoughts (Hebrews [England: Sheffield Academic Press, 1991], 66).

⁴⁸Frederick Fyvie Bruce argues that Christ did a great deal by delivering his people from the penalties of sin. He likewise redeemed them from its corruption and dominance and made way for their complete emancipation from its burdens (The Epistle of Paul to the Romans: An Introduction and Commentary [London: Inter-varsity Press, 1980], 520).

⁴⁹Brooke Foss Westcott, The Epistle to the Hebrews: The Greek text with Notes and Essays (Michigan, Grand Rapids: William B. Eerdmans, 1984), 278. Cf. Andrew B. Davidson, The Epistle to the Hebrews: In handbooks for Bible Classes and Private Students (Edinburgh: T. & T. Clark, 1882), 188.

⁵⁰George Eldon Ladd, A Theology of the New Testament (Michigan: Grand Rapids: William B. Eerdmans, 1993), 628.

⁵¹Owen, Hebrews, 163.

⁵²Franz Delitzsch, D.D., Commentary on the Epistle to the Hebrews, 2. (Minneapolis: Klock & Clock Christian Publishers, 1978), 160; Marcus Dods, The Epistle to the Hebrews: In the Expositor's Greek Testament (Grand Rapids: William B. Eerdmans, 1970), 4:344.

shedding of Christ's blood, God could not open heaven to us. The only sacrifice that God will admit is the perfect sacrifice of Christ⁵³. Standing before God guilty, heaven is shut to people unless they are allowed to enter because of Christ's death. Jesus's blood unbolted the door for believers, and it is based on that bloodshed that God will permit them into His holy presence in heaven. Jesus' blood saved the elect and sanctified their presence before the Father⁵⁴.

Ambrose and Mopsuestia asserted that Christ died for everyone apart from His deity⁵⁵. The researcher queries the usage of everyone, stating that although the atonement is for everyone, its efficacy is limited to the elect who believe in him.

Subsequently, Jesus had accomplished His agonizing work of the Cross, and He had to present that blood before the Father, a final priestly act⁵⁶. Young anchored the notion of Christ's sacrifice being once and for all. He opined that after AD 70, the church started to spiritualize sacrifice and cast off the tangible practice of sacrifices because the death of Christ was acknowledged as the perfect and final sacrifice that canceled all other sacrifices. This implies that Yahweh permitted the Israelites' sacrifices and, therefore, directed them to Him⁵⁷. Far ahead, after Jesus' crucifixion and the demolition of the temple in Jerusalem, the church withdrew from ritual sacrifices and used a spiritual language (Rom. 12:1; 1 Pt. 2:5) with reference to sacrifices.

The redemption of man is attributed to the blood of Christ, and this blood is sacrificially shed, precisely as the blood of bulls, goats, and calves was shed under the law. Once and for all, εφραπαξ, in opposition to the annual entry of the high priest into the holiest, with the blood of the annual victim. The holy place or sanctuary, τα ἁγία, signifies heaven, into which Jesus entered with his own blood, as the high priest entered into the holy of holies with the blood of the sacrificed victims⁵⁸.

In the Old Covenant, blood, ashes, water, and fire were external cleansing mechanisms (Num. 19:1-10). Their effects were known to be time-based because they removed ceremonial contamination and formed ceremonial sanctification. Furthermore, they repealed Israel's embarrassment of being removed from the Jewish church and reinstated them to society and adherence to the laws⁵⁹. Nonetheless, Christ's blood was superior to the Old Covenant blood, as it is of Himself and rinses spiritually, morally, and ritually; that is, Christ's blood purifies the sinful heart and external body⁶⁰. In this study, the researcher confirms that the sacrifices had to be repeated yearly, which exhibited the unfinished nature of the forgiveness. It removes the guilt for each year, but it has to be repeated.

Christ's Blood Offers In-depth Access to The Heavenly Holy of Holies (9:11-12).

The author determines the superiority of Jesus' sacrifice by examining the regularity with which the earthly high priest entered the Most Holy Place for atonement⁶¹. While the high priest, in the most solemn of all the rituals of the Jewish cultic system, still had to do this rite year after year, the difference is now clear, as Jesus' work in the

⁵³The author seeks to address the superiority of Christ's sacrifice from the perspective of sacrifice frequency and application. This is apparent in the number of times the author refers to the regularity with which even the Day of Atonement ritual, the most sacred of all feast-day rituals, had to be repeated (9:26-28; 10:1-4, 11-14). This frequency was required because no animal can take away sin and make anyone perfect (10:1-4). This is why God equipped the body of Christ as the final sacrifice for sin, which would only need to happen once (vs 5). By "one offering," Jesus has been able to perfect those who are being sanctified.

⁵⁴See Andrew Davidson said that the blood of Christ is the ransom paid to God that dissipates the liability of sin and sets man free from his captivity (The Epistle to the Hebrews: In Handbooks for Bible Classes and Private Students [Edinburgh: T. & T. Clark, 1882], 175)

⁵⁵Philip Edgcumbe Hughes, Commentary on the Epistle to the Hebrews (Michigan: Grand Rapids, 1977), 95.

⁵⁶George C. Fuller, "The Life of Jesus, after the Ascension (Luke 24:50-53, Acts 1:9-11)," The Westminster Theological Journal 56, no. 2 (1994): 393.

⁵⁷Frances Margaret Young, Sacrifice and the death of Christ (London: SPCK: 1975), 10-21.

⁵⁸Christ offered Himself on the cross, a once-and-for-all substitutionary sacrifice to God on behalf of the sins of the past, present, and future. There is no more payment required, as Jesus uttered "tetelestai" He professed forever.

⁵⁹For example, by his own blood shed for the forgiveness of sins. That blood was not spilled for himself for he had no sin and as a result there was a substantial dissimilarity between his offering and that of the Jewish high priest. The variance demonstrates that the offering made by Christ was wholly for others; that of the Jewish priest for himself as well as for them. The blood offered by the Jewish priest was that of animals; that offered by the savior was his own and that offered by the Jewish priest was only a sign for it could not cart off sin; that offered by Christ had a tangible value and eliminated disobedience from the soul.

⁶⁰Hagner, Encountering Hebrews, 122.

⁶¹Scholars have emphasized the importance of Jesus' entrance into the heavenly sanctuary and its unique and immeasurable outcomes. For example, Owen, Hebrews; Delitzsch, Commentary on the Epistle; Lenski, The interpretation of the Epistle to the Hebrews.

sanctuary had to be done only once. The implication is that as the Jewish high priest bore the blood of the animal into the Holy of Holies and spread it there as the cause of penitence, so the offering that Christ has to make in heaven is the blood that he shed on the cross. Having made the expiation, he presently beseeches the merit of it as a 'cause' why sinners should be redeemed. It does not entail that he literally bore his own blood into heaven as the high priest did the blood of the animals into the sanctuary or that he literally 'dotted' it on the mercy seat there, but that that blood, having been shed for sin, is now the basis of his pleading and intercession for the forgiveness of sin as the dotted blood of the Jewish sacrifice was the basis of the beseeching of the Jewish high priest for the forgiveness of himself and the people.

Jesus' ascension to heaven demonstrates a substantial point in Hebrews 9:11-14. Here, Jesus is designated as a high priest entering τὰ ἅγια with his own blood to acquire eternal salvation. This salvation is illuminated as the cleansing of the conscience that allows believers to worship the living God. There is a textual variant in 9:11. The best reading is "the good things that have come."⁶² The "greater and more perfect tabernacle, not made with hands," points to the "true tabernacle" in heaven (8:2), which is God's very presence." The trajectory to a new horizon shows that Christ did not just enter an earthly Holy of Holies. He went into heaven itself, of which the earthly tabernacle was only a picture of good things to come (Heb. 10:1), that is, a New Covenant and future receipt of direct access to God.⁶²

This entry into the holiest sanctuary symbolized the entrance into the presence of God, nearness to the reconciled Divinity, spiritual sanctuary, the throne of God or heaven itself⁶³. In addition, unlike the earthly priests, Christ's entrance only occurred once and cannot be repeated. Brown elaborates on the viewpoint that Christ, as the High Priest, will no longer die again to reunite us with God⁶⁴. To further expound, Christ did not take the blood of goats and calves to sprinkle on the altar. Instead, he went there through his own blood." Christ did not go into the heavenly sanctuary with His blood but through His blood." He secured our redemption on the cross. In contrast to going back annually, Christ entered the holy place once and for all, having obtained eternal redemption. The author displays the complete supremacy and conclusiveness of Christ's blood over the old system. Through His death, our guilt is atoned for once and for all, for all eternity. The punishment has been paid. There is nothing that we can add to what Christ did. Through Him, we have direct access to God.

In the Old Covenant, the animal to be sacrificed was to be spotless; similarly, Christ Himself was offered unblemished to God (Heb. 9:14).

Christ's Blood Affords Absolute Efficacy That Cleanses Our Consciences (9:13-14)

Christ's blood was superior to the Old Covenant blood, as it is of Himself and cleanses the sinful heart and external body spiritually, morally, and ritually⁶⁵. The blood of bulls and goats and the ashes of a heifer "sanctify the flesh." In addition to the Day of Atonement ritual, the author adds the red heifer ritual (Num. 19:1-13). This was a ritual for purification, especially if someone touched a dead body. The author argues from the lesser to the greater. If these rituals could cleanse the flesh, "how much more will the blood of Christ, who through the eternal Spirit offered Himself without blemish to God, cleanse your conscience from dead works to serve the living God?" Jesus Christ is the only one who could atone for man's sin because He alone was a man without blemish in all that He did. Thus, His blood can substitute for the penalty that we deserve.

⁶²Paul Ellingworth further explains that good things will come as forgiveness of sins (Heb. 10:17), perfection (Heb. 10:14), and consecration to God (Heb. 10:10, 14). The Old Covenant system had always been intended as a preparation, not as an end in itself (Heb. 10:5-6); hence, the blood of the animals sacrificed in the Old Covenant failed to secure perfection (The Epistle to the Hebrews [London: Epworth Press, 1991], 84).

⁶³Attridge, Harold W, Hebrews: Hermeneia: A Critical and Historical Commentary (Philadelphia: Fortress Press, 1989), 246.

⁶⁴John Brown, Hebrews (Edinburgh: The Banner of Truth Trust, 1976), 396.

⁶⁵Hagner, Encountering the Hebrews, 122; Bruce, the Epistle, 205.

Jesus' sacrifice was uniquely useful in redeeming His people because He is not only a man but also an eternal God (7:3, 16). The dissimilarity between the Levitical offerings and Christ's self-offering was infinite rather than relative⁶⁶. This infinitely effective sacrifice gratified God in a way that the blood of bulls and goats never could. Through Christ's blood, we can have a clean conscience. The Bible clarifies that the conscience alone is not an infallible guide. The conscience can be defiled (Titus 1:15) and seared through repeated sin (1 Tim 4:2). Therefore, our consciences must be educated and trained through Scripture. Acknowledging God and His holy principles, our consciences indict us of how sinful we are. God's work in regeneration is to clear our guilt and cleanse our consciences through the sacrifice of a satisfactory substitute. The Petrine epistle reveals that Christ also died for sins once and for all, the just for the unjust, so that He might bring us to God (1 Peter 3:18).

Morris, MacDonald, and Attridge corroborated that the blood-life sacrifice of Christ made eternal expiation for sins, inspiring the entire life, both externally and internally, redeeming the soul, mind, heart, and body, and turning forgiveness of sins into an eternally attained, living truth. Jesus's once-and-for-all blood-life sacrifice disseminates the Gospel that there is no more a sacrifice for sins because Jesus' blood-life sacrifice is ultimate (Heb 10:18). Just as a person dies once, so God resolved Christ to die once as an unblemished sacrifice. His second coming is for the salvation of those who believe in Him and for the judgment of those who reject Him⁶⁷.

Annulment and the Need for More Sacrifices

Christ's sacrifice was annulled, repealed, and all other sacrifices were concluded. God founded the Old Testament sacrifices as momentary and preparatory, not as a perpetual system (Heb. 10:5-6), and He never adored sacrifices, but rather the compliant heart (Heb. 10:6-7).

Christ's sacrifice on the cross was final⁶⁸. The author of Hebrews attests that there is no longer any offering for sin where there is forgiveness of sins (Heb. 10:18). There is no need for another sacrifice. Jesus paid it all. Christ's covenant was eternal, and His offering for sin was perfect; therefore, there is no longer any need for any other offering for sin. God imputed all our sins to Jesus Christ, who died in our place as our representative. Moreover, He also imputed to us all the perfect righteousness of Jesus Christ, and now we have a perfect standing before Him for all eternity. The beautiful thing about this new covenant is that God is a perfect forgetter; He no longer remembers our sins. 'Their sins and their lawless deeds I will remember no more' (Heb. 10: 18). This is true because Jesus died, and His blood covers all our lawless deeds⁶⁹.

The Holy Spirit is at work in the hearts of true believers, relating to them the great message of redemption. In verses 15-18, the Holy Spirit and Yahweh are one. What the Holy Spirit says is what God says. The author of Hebrews had a high view of the inspiration of the Scriptures and believed in the Trinity. The theme of the new covenant is picked up once again and applied to the believer⁷⁰.

The Imminence of the Human Blood Sacrifice of the Imborvungu Cult: The Deity of Good Things to Come (fertility, prosperity, and riches)

Bloody human sacrifice falls under the loudest condemnation of biblical faith (e.g., The lev 18:). However, the prevalent impact of imborivungu is a longstanding tradition in Tiv land, for those who seek prosperity are required to perform an unceasing sacrifice of human blood, spilt to satisfy the deity. This practice is against Christ's atonement. Some members of Christian communities in the Tiv nation, even those that the Dutch Reformed

⁶⁶Edgecombe, Commentary on the Epistle, 360.

⁶⁷Morris, W. (1971) Hebrews, Bible study. The Epistle to the Hebrews: From Ritual to Reality, New Jersey: Loizeaux Brothers; the Epistle to the Hebrews (Philadelphia: Fortress, 1989).

⁶⁸Christ's sacrifice annulled and removed our sin, penalty, and curse from us, like the scapegoat which was sent away by the priest (Dunnil, Covenant and Sacrifice, 172).

⁶⁹Psalms 103: 12 portrays that as far as the east is from the west, so far has He removed our transgressions from us. Romans 8: 1 corroborates that because our sins are under His blood, God has forgiven and forgotten all of them. They are cast into the depths of the sea. "Therefore, there is now no condemnation for those who are in Christ Jesus.

⁷⁰Jeremiah 33: 32-34.

Christian Mission evangelized, have subscribed to this exercise as a potential for good things to come (fertility, prosperity, and riches).

The message of Hebrews portrays that Jesus Christ is better, greater, superior, and more effective than any figure, occurrence, or setup in the Old Testament. Christ's sacrifice annulled any subsequent sacrifice, including imborivungu.

According to Iordam Uke, when Imborvungu is involved, human sacrifice is inevitable. A typical Tiv man who wants to showcase his affluence kills either of the following to spill blood for sacrifice by empowering the deity to display her power of fortune:⁷¹ This is the normal godly approach, 'gbaaondo', an effective and efficient way to secure wealth. Uke narrated an incident where a man came to their ancestral home, the Tse-Igbe family, and took away imborivungu. No one challenged him, but after a distance of 3 km, a woman in their family rose and chased after the man overpowered and killed them after a place called Ortese in Ipav, and brought back imborivungu. He revealed that it is being practiced today with vigor, even among Christians⁷².

The Imborvungu cult requires consecutive human sacrifices to maintain its custody. The most important of the great Akombo is the Imborivungu, or owl-pipe, a small object originally made from a human tibia, but more recently made out of brass. However, this is not the case with the Tiv. Rather, the Imborivungu is regarded as Akombo and is regularly "repaired" to "repair the land." Mbatsav who are elders and tsav custodians usually make use of imborivungu cultic emblem to perform akombo rites to remedy the land⁷³.

In Akiga Story, there is personal Imborivungu and that of the Fathers. It is a personal imborivungu that is transformed into an imborivungu of the fathers for the group to set right the land. This change occurs when the group persuades the custodian to part with it for the mutual good. However, if the custodian is very elusive, the custodian is postponed until he dies, and then the senior elder induces his children to give it to him⁷⁴. The entire group then set out to set the land right with it. The man who fetches it keeps custody of it, but the group owns it. In addition, when it turns into the business of the entire group, profound measures are employed; a human life is needed, rather than a mouse, which was used when it was the asset of a single person. A man is slaughtered, or a baby or a fetus is obtained from an aborted woman. Nonetheless, it must be a woman who has not given birth before⁷⁵.

Others slaughter babies through the secret way to set right the imborivungu⁷⁶. When mbatsav elders agree to sacrifice a baby, they trick the mother of the child. They take the baby's dead body and bury it. Subsequently, during the night, they dig up again and set the imborivungu with it, in the same way as they did with the abortion. The land prospers. Shortly after, the woman bears another baby. The elders vow that no harm will affect the baby⁷⁷.

⁷¹Iordam Uke, (Retired Soldier, Gboko), Interview by Abel Aor Inyaregh, Gboko, December 31, 2024.

⁷²Uke, Interview.

⁷³The imborivungu is indispensable to the Tiv people; it is used for setting right the land and has a much greater worth than you would assess from its outlook. It is a human bone; some say it is a shin bone, others say it is taken from the arm. It appears more like an arm bone, which is barely huge enough for a shin bone unless conceivably that of a small child. When a man dies, his corpse is dug up by a mbatsav, who takes one of the bones to construct imboivungu to set right the land. The bone is cut down to about the length of a man's hand (they are not all the matching size, but all are made in the same manner). Then, some clothes are tied around the top and enclosed in wax, and on top it is stuck with some hair and sometimes some love beans. Two cowrie shells are attached in the wax to appear like eyes and some more red beans are attached on either side for the raised face markings. It also has a mouth, nose, and ears. Similarly, the imborivungu may be made of metal. This type is cast in brass and is constructed after the same design as the bone type, not including wax, and its head is brass all through. Some have male heads and some have female heads, as in the case of those made of bones. When it is finished, a hole is bored in its chest, the bottom end is stopped up with wax, and some spider's web hangs on top of this. In appreciation of its self-esteem, the imborivungu is ornamented with the finest beads. See Akiga's Story: The Tiv Tribe as viewed by one of its members. Rupert East (Ibadan: Caltop Publications Limited, 2003), 2 48-49.

⁷⁴Akiga's Story, 250.

⁷⁵Akiga's Story, 250.

⁷⁶During the nighttime baby ritual sacrifice, the elders gather as everyone is asleep, the caretaker of the imborivungu conveys it, and the rites launches with the dead fetus. The man who has been concealing it places it on the floor, and alongside it, they place the imborivungu and a calabash filled with water. First, they take the fetus, make passes with it, and cut its throat with a knife. They smear some of the blood on the imborivungu. When they have finished, they wash their hands in the calabash vessel, then pour the water into a well and over the farm of the keeper of the imborivungu. As a result, the harvests of the whole group will be bountiful, and the first woman to draw water from the well the next morning will immediately get pregnant and bear a son, even though she had previously been infertile (Akiga's Story, 251-252).

⁷⁷Akiga's Story, 252.

Imborivungu can be sold secretly, as stated by Sai Story, which explains that the seller coaches the buyer on how to perform its rites to set it right⁷⁸. The imborivungu is set aside in a box, and everything else that is put in it gets an advantage from it. If you wear stuff that has been touched by it, you will definitely win the day. No one at the ceremony will be able to challenge you⁷⁹.

The imborivungu or owl-pipe was very popular during the period of the witchcraft enquiry in 1929, for it was an ill-famed object in the apparatus of the mbatsav, and its cult was one of those which was held to require human sacrifice⁸⁰. Asserting from a different angle, Iordam Uke said Imborvungu is the god or deity of Tiv people that has been practiced in Tiv Culture for a long period of time. It is very helpful in terms of prosperity. Imborvungu has power that is demonstrated. There is an act designated as “dura imborvungu,” which means “tongues.” When that happens, you have a bountiful harvest⁸¹.

The Tiv ritual purification of the tar to ensure the fertility of human beings, animals, crops, and the land affected through the akombo of imborvungu, demonstrates the desire of the people to increase their tribal numbers. Abortion is the killing of human life and is condemned because it is opposed to the fulfillment of this desire. The Tiv elders may lament that event because during the colonial and missionary period, imborvungu emblems were confiscated and the ritual practice was prohibited, while the akombo remained steadfast in imparting traditional values, which stand opposed to the practice of abortion.

According to Kaaondo, imborivungu is an idol that Tiv people believe has the capacity to help them and bring good luck to their doorsteps. Its image looks like a baby. In the middle, it is composed of a baby’s bone, and the eyes are made of isheshoho, the seed of a plant that looks exactly like an eye. The head is made of skin, and a liquid mixture is poured inside⁸².

Kaaondo asserts that the Tiv have three ways of taking custody of imborivungu. First, it is patrilineal ownership: in one’s kinsmen, they chop it according to doors and family lines. Second, it is matrilineal ownership: this one belongs to one’s mother’s kinsmen. This happens when a female child is getting married and has been loved so much by her father. The father gives her imborivungu to ensure her prosperity and good luck. It is considered a blessing from the father to the daughter. The daughter is said to have been her father’s firstborn. Going by the tradition of imborivungu, if the normal norm is violated by giving it to the second-born instead of the firstborn, the second child will automatically die⁸³.

Third, Iortsor asserts that the acquisition of imborivungu comes from the family buying it for prosperity. Whenever an interested and ambitious person goes to the imborivungu market to buy, his kinsmen are already aware of the situation, which is spiritually alarming. As you brought the idol into your home, if any of your kinsmen overpowers you, he will snatch it from your hands. This is not ordinary; it is a spiritual tussle. In another way, your kinsmen may gang up collectively to snatch it from you and give it to your neighbor, whom they feel should enjoy it. Or ityo will ask you to give it to them to keep it for you, so they will eventually kill you and spill the blood on it, and they, in turn, will give it to another person of their choice. He commented literally that, ‘if your vanger (chest) is not strong,’ implying that you are not spiritually fit or strong⁸⁴.

It is attested that in those days, when the Tiv people were not well familiarized with schooling, imborivungu was their benchmark for farming because it yields bountiful harvests and enables them to live in affluence. Thus, the person who keeps custody of imborivungu is an older adult’s person in charge of the family ‘orya’ and the person

⁷⁸Akiga’s Story, 249-250.

⁷⁹Akiga’s Story, 252.

⁸⁰Akiga’s Story, 252.

⁸¹Uke, interview.

⁸²Kaaondo Iortsor, (Security officer, SORA International, Gboko), Interview by Abel Aor Inyaregh, Gboko, 2024.

⁸³Iortsor, Interview.

⁸⁴Iortsor, Interview.

who enjoys the affluence is designated as a different person. The person it is allotted to enjoys it very well and rotates according to clans. After the one enjoying it dies, it goes to another family line. The one keeping it is different from the one enjoying it. It is the one keeping it alongside kinsmen who provide sacrificial fowls, which human sacrifice, to keep it going.

It gets to a time, imborivungu proves to be weak or ineffective. Consequently, they would kill family members to spill blood to strengthen their power.

Siblings fight over imborivungu to keep custody of it and enjoy it. If the father intends to bless the second child, he will be tempted to kill the first to give it to the second, since it is ordinarily supposed to be given to the firstborn. If not, ityo (patrilineal kinsmen) will kill the second-born because the protocol is not observed.

If someone sees it, he will pay with his life, and Iortsor agrees that it is practiced till today.

Iortsor believes that Imborivungu is a blood-sucking deity, a god Tiv believed helps them in times of need. Imborivungu has the power to vibrate (*dura imborivungu*) and activate the bountiful harvest of yam tubers. It is known for sacrificing human beings and spilling blood to sustain its powers. Tiv has been carving wooden drums (*indyer-yiase*), which attract blood spills. Not everyone was gifted to perform this craft work; an appointed family member was chosen for this purpose. At times, ityo (one's kinsmen) were mandated to keep custody of imborivungu, someone in the beneficiary's family line is used for ritual sacrifice. Relations in a family line where imborivungu is domiciled, at times, in scrambling to keep possession of the god fight among themselves and kill one another (*ve kuma ayol ve*)⁸⁵.

The practice of imborivungu was prominent during the time of Jato Aka, when the demand for witchcraft artifacts was requested to be handed over (*Na akaa*) because it had to do with killing people, and the Englishman era frowned on it⁸⁶. Igotor exclaimed that Tiv had fought wars and had slaves. He narrated an incident where kinsmen were fighting to take possession of imborivungu, and Kpela used a rope to tie his brother to a tree. The corpse was not there when the grave was opened. Whiteman asked Kpela to bring imborivungu where he had taken it⁸⁷. The reason for imborivungu is for a bountiful harvest, prosperity, and riches; one gets plenty of money to have a happy family. During the dancing competition anniversary, a person will come to borrow imborivungu to win, and the person in question will give a chicken (human) as payment. In the case that he fails to do the needful, the person dies⁸⁸.

Uke, Iortsor, and Igotor all agreed that imborivungu involved human sacrifice, and it is still a symbol of prosperity. Moreover, the Imborivungu cult dragged its adherents into cannibalism, whereby the human body was butchered and eaten at night by those who belonged to the Imborivungu cult. A wooden mat has been used to divide the human body into parts and distribute them among the clans represented. Blood was useful. It is used at night; the star provides light to their path. Both men and women are being sacrificed.

Conclusion

Thus, theological inventiveness can remodel people's understanding of what they are and require. Hebrews 9 articulates how a new truth originated in Christ's death and ascension that annihilated the necessity for people to offer sacrifices to be in the right relationship with God and fellow humans. The obscurity and fragility of human disorder create a lacuna in the need for sacrifice. Nonetheless, Hebrews 9 directs human life in a new direction,

⁸⁵For example, the person who is chosen to enjoy it, unless he dies, otherwise imborivungu remains with him. The ritual of renewing it continues, especially when it is weak and not performing well. Family members are used for sacrifice to empower. It can move to another family when the one prospering because of it dies. The person who is interested in taking it must kill to claim it. Under normal circumstances, the protocol demands that it be handed over to the elderly son. However, if the elderly woman who might be in charge loves the second son more than the first and is determined to give it to the second son, she decides to kill her first issue so that the second issue will inherit it. However, if the kinsmen frown at it, they might decide to kill the second son out of rage, and that is how imboivungu would finally depart from that lineage. If someone, peradventure sees imborivungu, will surely pay for his dear life. The practice is ongoing.

⁸⁶Dwen Adam Igotor, (Community elder). Interview by Abel Aor Inyaregh, Gboko, December 17, 2024.

⁸⁷Igotor, Interview.

⁸⁸Igotor, Interview.

the trajectory of good things to come. This is a life without sacrifice, which underscores the significance of Jesus' sacrificial death, resurrection, and ascension in a way that brings unimaginable redemption.

The inventiveness of the Hebrews regarding the reconceptualisation of sacrifice cannot be overestimated. The theology in Hebrews is dynamic, moving cogently into the future manifestation of the new covenant that the prophet Jeremiah confirmed regarding the Mosaic covenant (Jer 31:31-34). Jeremiah spoke of God's law being written on human hearts, internalized by the Holy Spirit, which does not require physical sacrifices to make it right with God, as claimed by custodians of imborivungu. The author of Hebrews recurrently cited and referenced this innovation when interpreting rebirth. The old agreement is discarded, forgotten, and will not be remembered forever (Heb 8:8-12, 13 and 10:15-17).

One of the most significant contributions of the letter to the Hebrews to Christology is its unique emphasis on the high priesthood of Christ. No other New Testament writing offers such a descriptive picture of Christ's installation as a high priest, his process of perfection, or his entry into the heavenly sanctuary and subsequent offering for sin. Generally, Hebrews offers the most vibrant picture of Christ's high priesthood ministry in action, one that meticulously follows the movement of the Levitical high priest on Yom Kippur.

The irrefutable deduction portrays that there is no longer an offering for sin. Those who have been redeemed no longer need to sacrifice animals. To offer sacrifices for sin would be unscriptural and would indicate a lack of faith in Christ's finished work. Christ's once-for-all sacrifice for sin justifies believers, and they need nothing more. The blood of the animals could not be redeemed. However, through His death, Jesus Christ removed the sins of many people. As the author of Hebrews warns, Imborivungu, which requires human sacrifice, is inimical to Christ's sacrifice and is capable of leading people to apostasy.

Bibliography

Akiga. Akiga's Story: The Tiv Tribe as Seen by One of Its Members. Translated by Rupert East. Caltop Publications Limited, 2003.

Attridge, Harold W. Hebrews: A Commentary. Hermeneia: A Critical and Historical Commentary Fortress Press, 1989.

Attridge, Harold W. "Epistle to the Hebrews." In The Anchor Bible Dictionary, edited by David Noel Freedman. Doubleday, 1992.

Bruce, Frederick Fyvie. The Epistle to the Hebrews. The New International Commentary on the New Testament Rev. ed. Eerdmans, 1990.

Brown, John. Hebrews. Edinburgh: The Banner of Truth Trust, 1976.

Brown, Raymond E. "Pilgrimage in Faith: The Christian Life in Hebrews." Southwestern Journal of Theology 28, no. 1 (1985): 28–35.

Calvin, John. The Epistle of Paul the Apostle to the Hebrews and St. Peter's First and Second Epistles. Eerdmans, 1963.

Chester, Arthur N. "Hebrews: The final sacrifice." In Sacrifice and Redemption, edited by S. W. Sykes, 57–72. Cambridge University Press, 1991.

- Cockerill and Gareth Lee Epistle to the Hebrews. The New International Commentary on the New Testament. Eerdmans, 2012.
- Davidson, Andrew B. The Epistle to the Hebrews: In Handbooks for Bible Classes and Private Students. New York: Oxford University Press. T. & T. Clark, 1882.
- Delitzsch, Franz. Commentary on the Epistle to the Hebrews. 2 vols. Vol. 2. Klock and Klock Christian Publishers, 1978.
- Dods, Marcus. Epistle to the Hebrews. In The Expositor's Greek Testament. Eerdmans, 1970.
- Dunnill, John. Covenant and Sacrifice in the Letter to the Hebrews. Cambridge University Press, 1992.
- Edgcumbe Philip Hughes. Commentary on the Epistle to the Hebrews. Baker Book House, 1977.
- Ellingworth, Paul. Epistle to the Hebrews. Epworth Press, 1991.
- Fuller, G. C. (1994). "The Life of Jesus, after the Ascension (Luke 24:50–53, Acts 1:9–11)." The Westminster Theological Journal 56, no. 2 (1994): 389–406.
- Gossai, H., ed. Studies in Biblical Literature: The King-Priest of Psalm 110 in the Hebrews. Lang, P. (2001).
- Gordon, Robert P. Hebrews. Sheffield Academic Press, 1991.
- Guthrie, Donald. The Letter to the Hebrews: An Introduction and Commentary. Inter-Varsity Press, 1983.
- Hagner, Donald A. Encountering Hebrews: An Exposition. Baker Academic, 2002.
- Hawthorne, Gerald F. "Hebrews." In Zondervan Pictorial Encyclopedia of the Bible, edited by Merrill C. Tenney. New York: Harper Books; 2010. Zondervan, 2008.
- Hughes, Philip Edgcumbe. Commentary on the Epistle to the Hebrews. Eerdmans, 1977.
- Igotor, Dwen Adam. Interview with Abel Aor Inyaregh. Gboko, December 17, 2024.
- Inyaregh, A. A. Interview with Iordam Uke Gboko, December 31, 2024.
- Inyaregh, A. A. Interview with Iortsor Kaaondo Gboko, January 2, 2024.
- Johnson, Luke Timothy. Hebrews: A Commentary. Westminster John Knox Press, 2006.
- Kent, H. A., Jr. The Epistle to the Hebrews: A Commentary. Baker Book House, 1974.

Lane, William L. Hebrews 9–13. Word Biblical Commentary 47B. Word Books, 1991.

Lenski, R. C. H. The interpretation of the Epistle to the Hebrews and the Epistle of James. Augsburg Publishing House, 1966.

Lindars, Barnabas. Theology of the Letter to the Hebrews. Cambridge University Press, 1991.

Luther, Martin. 1909. “Christ Our Great High Priest.” In *The Sermons of Martin Luther*, 7:163–167. Minneapolis, MN: The Luther Press, 1909.

MacDonald, William. *The Epistle to the Hebrews: From Ritual to Reality*. Loizeaux Brothers, 1971.

Marshall, I. Howard. *New Testament Theology: Many Witnesses, One Gospel*. Inter-Varsity Press, 2004.

Moffitt, David M. Atonement and the Logic of Resurrection in the Epistle to the Hebrews. *Novum Testamentum*, 141. Brill, 2011.

Morris, Leon. Hebrews. Bible Study Commentary. Zondervan, 1988.

Morris, Leon. *The New Testament Theology*. Zondervan, 1986.

Owen, John. Hebrews: The Epistle of the Warning. Kregel Publications, 1968.

Scholer, J. M. Proleptic Priests: Priesthood in the Epistle of Hebrews. *Journal for the Study of the New Testament*, 49. Sheffield: JSOT Press, 1991.

Schrenk, K. G. “Role of Priests.” In *Theological Dictionary of the New Testament*, edited by Gerhard Kittel and Gerhard Friedrich. Eerdmans, 1988.

Shiffman, Lawrence H. “Temple, Sacrifice, and Priesthood in the Epistle to the Hebrews and the Dead Sea Scrolls.” In *Echoes from the Caves: Qumran and the New Testament*, edited by Florentino García Martínez, 169–188. Leiden: Brill, 2009.

Smith, R. H. *Augsburg Commentary on the New Testament: Hebrews*. Augsburg Publishing House, 1984.

Tappert, Theodore G., ed. *Luther’s Works*. Vol. 35. Fortress Press, 1955.

Thompson, J. W. (1979). “Hebrews 9 and the Hellenistic Concept of Sacrifice.” *Journal of Biblical Literature* 98, no. 4 (1979): 567–578.

Uke, Iordam. Interview with Abel Aor Inyaregh. Gboko, December 31, 2024.

Ullucci, Daniel C. *The Christian rejection of animal sacrifice*. Oxford University Press, 2012.

Westcott and Brooke Foss *Epistle to the Hebrews: Greek Text with Notes and Essays* Eerdmans, William B. 1984.

Young, Frances Margaret. *Sacrifice and the Death of Christ*. SPCK, 1975.